

Supplementary Material 2

Results

Cereal yield, yield stability, and nitrous oxide release in European conservation agriculture: a meta-analysis

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Table S1. Results for random-effects meta-regressions that show statistically significant relationships between the relative yield ($\ln(R)$) and continuous explanatory variables (a) topsoil clay content in soils, (b) tillage depth in conservation agriculture, (c) mineral N fertilizer and their combined effects: (d) topsoil clay content \times tillage depth in conservation agriculture (CA), (e) mineral N fertilizer \times tillage depth in CA, (f) topsoil clay content \times mineral N fertilizer.

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(a) Topsoil clay content

Predictor	Value	Standard Error	95% CI		<i>p</i> -value (χ^2)
			Low	Up	
β_0 (intercept)	0.0227	0.0175	-0.0116	0.0571	0.1941
β_1 (Clay)	-0.0017	0.0005	-0.0027	-0.0006	0.0019

Heterogeneity

Source	<i>Qm</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i> -value (χ^2)
Model	9.7	1	0.0019
Error	49.6	52	0.5679
Total	59.3	53	0.2568

(b) Tillage depth

Predictor	Value	Standard Error	95% CI		<i>p</i> -value (χ^2)
			Low	Up	
β_0 (intercept)	-0.0481	0.0145	-0.0766	-0.0196	0.0009
β_1 (Tillage depth)	0.0030	0.0015	0.0001	0.0058	0.0415

Heterogeneity

Source	<i>Qm</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i> -value (χ^2)
Model	4.2	1	0.0415
Error	50.9	56	0.6649
Total	55.1	57	0.5454

(c) Mineral N fertilizer

Predictor	Value	Standard Error	95% CI		<i>p</i> -value (χ^2)
			Low	Up	
β_0 (intercept)	0.0567	0.0310	-0.0041	0.1174	0.0674
β_1 (Mineral N fertilizer)	-0.0006	0.0002	-0.0011	-0.0002	0.0074

Heterogeneity

Source	<i>Qm</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i> -value (χ^2)
Model	7.2	1	0.0074
Error	45.4	51	0.6962
Total	52.5	52	0.4531

(d) Topsoil clay content × Tillage depth in conservation agriculture

Predictor	Value	Standard Error	95% CI		<i>p</i> -value (χ^2)
			Low	Up	
β_0 (intercept)	0.0000	0.0224	-0.0439	0.0440	0.9991
β_1 (Clay)	-0.0015	0.0005	-0.0026	-0.0005	0.0032
β_2 (Tillage depth CA)	0.0023	0.0013	-0.0003	0.0049	0.0864

Heterogeneity

Source	Q_m	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i> -value (χ^2)
Model	15.2	2	0.0005
Error	50.2	51	0.5042
Total	65.4	53	0.1170

(e) Mineral N fertilizer × Tillage depth in conservation agriculture

Predictor	Value	Standard Error	95% CI		<i>p</i> -value (χ^2)
			Low	Up	
β_0 (intercept)	0.0311	0.0284	-0.0246	0.0869	0.2736
β_1 (Mineral N fertilizer)	-0.0006	0.0002	-0.0010	-0.0002	0.0026
β_2 (Tillage depth CA)	0.0030	0.0011	0.0007	0.0052	0.0087

Heterogeneity

Source	Q_m	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i> -value (χ^2)
Model	16.1	2	0.0003
Error	48.6	50	0.5280
Total	64.7	52	0.1107

(f) Topsoil clay content × Mineral N fertilizer

Predictor	Value	Standard Error	95% CI		<i>p</i> -value (χ^2)
			Low	Up	
β_0 (intercept)	0.0965	0.0288	0.0401	0.1529	0.0008
β_1 (Clay)	-0.0018	0.0005	-0.0028	-0.0008	0.0002
β_2 (Mineral N fertilizer)	-0.0005	0.0002	-0.0009	-0.0001	0.0090

Heterogeneity

Source	Q_m	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i> -value (χ^2)
Model	21.9	2	0.0000
Error	42.3	47	0.6658
Total	64.3	49	0.0705

Table S2. Results for random-effects meta-regressions between the relative yield ($\ln(R)$) and other continuous explanatory variables (moderators) that show no statistically significant relationship.

Category	Continuous moderators	Q_m	df	p -value (χ^2)
Climate	Annual precipitation	1.39	1,57	0.239
	Annual average temperature	1.22	1,57	0.268
Soil	Silt	0.03	1,53	0.849
	Sand	3.76	1,53	0.052
	Soil pH	0.15	1,51	0.695
	Soil organic carbon	2.94	1,44	0.086
Agronomic management	n. crops in rotation	2.74	1,57	0.097
	CA duration	2.26	1,57	0.132

Table S3. Results for subgroup analysis examining the effects of categorical explanatory variables (moderators) on the relative yield ($\ln(R)$).

Category	Moderators	Q_b	df	p -value (χ^2)
Climate	European Environmental Zone	8.40	8,56	0.395
Agronomic management	Type of cereals	10.3	2,49	0.006
	Legumes in rotation	0.10	1,57	0.747
	Cover crops	1.24	1,57	0.264

Table S4. Results for random-effects meta-regressions between the relative coefficient of temporal yield variation ($\ln(CVR)$), i.e., inverse measure of yield stability, and continuous explanatory variables (moderators).

Category	Moderators	Q_m	df	p -value (χ^2)
Climate	Annual precipitation	2.06	1,49	0.151
	Annual average temperature	0.49	1,49	0.479
Soil	Topsoil clay	0.05	1,45	0.814
	Silt	0.04	1,45	0.830
	Sand	0.78	1,45	0.375
	Soil pH	0.14	1,44	0.704
	Soil organic carbon	0.62	1,37	0.428
Agronomic management	Tillage depth CA	1.46	1,49	0.237
	n. crops in rotation CA	0.47	1,49	0.489
	Mineral N fertilisation	2.17	1,47	0.140
	CA duration	0.42	1,49	0.519

Table S5. Results for subgroup analysis examining the effects of categorical explanatory variables (moderators) on the relative coefficient of temporal yield variation ($\ln(CVR)$), i.e., inverse measure of yield stability.

Category	Variable	Q_b	df	p -value (χ^2)
Climate	European Environmental Zone	3.22	7,47	0.863
Agronomic management	Type of cereals	1.45	2,42	0.484
	Legumes in rotation	0.54	1,49	0.459
	Cover crops	0.31	1,49	0.578

Table S6. Results for random-effects meta-regressions (Q_m) examining the effects of explanatory variables (moderators) on relative N_2O emissions, $\ln(R_{N2O})$.

Category	Variable	Q_m	df	p -value (χ^2)
Climatic	Annual precipitation	0.053	1,10	0.818

	Annual average temperature	0.276	1,10	0.598
Soil	Topsoil clay	15.23	1,9	<0.0001^a
Agronomic management	Mineral N fertilisation	3.28	1,10	0.070
	CA duration	0.09	1,10	0.755
Experiment	Duration of monitoring period	0.41	1,10	0.524

^a ID2 Baggs et al. (2003) was excluded as an outlier.

Table S7. Egger's regression-based test¹ enabling the publication bias for (a) cereal yield, (b) temporal yield variation, i.e., yield stability and (c) N₂O emissions.

(a) Yield

Parameter	Coefficient	Std. Error	t	p
Intercept	-0.020	0.0172	-1.137	0.260
Standard Error of ln (R)	-0.122	0.2287	-0.534	0.596

¹Random-effects meta-regression.

(b) The coefficient of temporal yield variation (inverse measure of yield stability)

Parameter	Coefficient	Std. Error	t	p
Intercept	0.087	0.1276	0.682	0.498
Standard Error of ln (CVR)	-0.006	0.3410	-0.018	0.986

(c) N₂O emissions

Parameter	Coefficient	Std. Error	t	p
Intercept	0.127	0.4118	0.309	0.765
Standard Error of ln (R_{N2O})	-0.516	1.4200	-0.363	0.725

Figure S1. (a) Boxplot of the relative coefficient of temporal yield variation (inverse measure of yield stability), $\ln(CVR)$. Outliers are highlighted in red, identified with interquartile (IQR) methods: ID1 Ali et al. (2019); ID4.2 Arvidsson et al. (2010); ID12 Dimassi et al. (2014); ID18 Kisić et al. (2010); ID19 Krauss et al. (2020); ID26 Maltas et al. (2013); ID42.2 Tørresen et al. (1999). Whiskers represent the range of data within 1.5 times the IQR range. (b) Normal Quantile plot of $\ln(CVR)$. The standardized effect size is the effect size divided by the square-root of its variance. The dashed silver line represents the regression and the solid silver lines the 95% prediction envelope. Red circle indicates outlier ID21.2 Lampurlanés et al. (2016).

Figure S2. Scatter plots between average yield in conventional systems and effect sizes (a) $\ln(R)$ and (b) $\ln(CVR)$. Q_m , model heterogeneity, and n is the number of independent studies. The dashed line indicates conventional agriculture (CONV). The symbol size corresponds to study weight.

Figure S3. Weighted meta-regressions between the duration of conservation agriculture and (a) the relative yield, $\ln(R)$, (b) the relative coefficient of temporal yield variation, $\ln(CVR)$, functioning as an inverse measure of yield stability, and (c) relative N₂O emissions, $\ln(R_{N_2O})$. The size of symbol corresponds to study weight, and the number indicates study ID. Q_m , model heterogeneity, and n is the number of independent studies.

Figure S4. Standard Deviation (σ) of the cereals yield change (%) computed with Monte Carlo simulations. More than 3 billion simulations were performed on an HPC system equipped with a 72 cores CPU, 756 GB of RAM, and an Nvidia RTX A4000 GPU. The total computational time was approximately 2 hours.

Figure S5. The 95% GLM Confidence Intervals (CIs) of lower and the upper bounds of cereal yield change (%) due to CA under two tillage scenario: no-tillage, NT (a, b) and minimum tillage, MT (c, d), adhering to the core principles of CA, compared to conventional agriculture.

Figure S6. Funnel plots for (a) $\ln (R)$, (b) $\ln (CVR)$ and (c) $\ln (R_{N20})$ versus precision, displaying the results of a Trim and Fill Analysis (Duval and Tweedie 2000). Blue circles represent the original data points, while red circles indicate inferred "missing" data. The red dashed line represents the original estimates of effect sizes; black solid line represents the revised estimate of effect size, assuming three (a) and two (b) missing studies. Numbers represent studies' IDs.